

Research

Effects of green vegetation's and organic waste on the productivity vis-à-vis nutrient status of vermicompost

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Abstract: Excessive and continuous use of chemical fertilizers and no use or less use of organic matter in to soil leads to the decline in productivity and soil health. Vermicompost, produced from industrial byproducts and local bio waste materials, could be an ideal supplement for chemical fertilizers in the tea industry of Bangladesh. The research was carried out at Luskerpore Tea Estate, Habiganj to assess their potential and effects on the qualitative characteristics of vermicompost. Different raw materials along with the cow-dung and *Eisenia foetida* were applied in seven dissimilar treatments with three replications. The productivity, as well as physicochemical properties pH, organic carbon (OC), nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), zinc (Zn), sulfur (S) of the finished product were evaluated. The nutrient properties were found high with the treatment T₄ as well as the highest productivity 71.80% was found with treatment T₄ where cow-dung, kitchen residues and *Eisenia foetida* were applied.

Keywords: Benefit-cost analysis, Cow-dung, *Eisenia foetida*, green vegetation, Tea

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Introduction

Tea is a perennial crop which requires optimum amount of macro- and micronutrients to grow and produce sustainable crops. Tea cannot be produced optimally without addition of external nutrient as well as fertilizer application. [1] Wang *et al.* reported that application of chemical fertilizer is the primary method used to maintain tea yield and quality but has a negative environmental impact owing to its enormous use. Enormous use of inorganic fertilizers leads to

deterioration of soil physical, chemical and biological properties, air pollution through nitrous oxide gas emission and excessive leaching leads to ground water pollution by nitrate and heavy metals. [2] Singh *et al.* reported that use of chemical fertilizer without soil fertility conservation not only depletes soil nutrient reserves but also disrupts the biological eco balance of the soil-plant system. Therefore, in recent years to meet the increasing demand for tea, crop production techniques has been shifting to environmentally safe and economically viable alternatives. Manmade fertilizers, mainly organic fertilizers containing nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K), have increased the output of agricultural products [3]. Therefore, organic manuring processes should be considered an important strategy for the sustainable agricultural production in the developing countries [4]. The application of nutrients through organic sources stimulates the activity of soil microorganisms, improves the structure of soil, increases plant nutrient holding capacity and increases the availability of plant nutrients. [2] Singh *et al.* again reported that the use of vermicompost as a source of organic matter has been proven to be a sound soil amendment and fertility management process.

Vermicomposting is the method of preparing enriched compost with the use of Redworms. It is one of the easiest methods to recycle agricultural waste and produce quality compost. Redworms consume biomass and excrete it in the digested form called worm casts which is rich in humus and nutrients. Vermicompost is greatly humified through the fragmentation of the parent organic materials by Redworm colonization by microorganisms [5]. The result of this process is the production of such products being odorless, light and peat like with high porosity, aeration, drainage, high water retention capacity, modified pH, low electrical conductivity (EC), high cation exchange capacity (CEC) and high microbial activity [6,7]. Vermicompost contains water soluble nutrients and is an excellent nutrient rich organic fertilizer as well as soil conditioner [8]. Besides organic enrichment, it improves the physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil [9, 10].

Vermicompost plays an important role in the agricultural sector of Bangladesh [11]. Though recently, different research on vermicompost is conducting in our agricultural sector, but for the tea industry of Bangladesh the present research on vermicompost production technology will fall an impact on good quality tea production which is very essential. It might be a cost effective production technology of organic fertilizer for the tea industry of Bangladesh. The tea sector depends mainly on imported and costly agrochemical such as, chemical fertilizers and pesticides. Replacement of these chemical fertilizers by the vermicompost can be a sustainable technology for the improvement of tea yield as well as tea quality. Moreover, it will protect the soil and environment from the pollution. Therefore, this type of research was conducted to develop a technology for the production of high quality vermicompost by the locally available green vegetation, residues and organic waste materials with minimum cost of production.

Materials and method

Experimental design for vermicompost

An experiment was carried out at Luskerpore Tea Estate located at Habiganj district of Bangladesh to observe the potential of different green vegetation and residues along with cow-dung and epigamic Redworm (*Eisenia foetida*) on the productivity as well as the effects on the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of vermicompost. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with seven treatments and three replications. The treatment was designed on the basis of locally availability of raw materials. The treatment combinations are given in table 1 below:

<i>Treatments</i>	
<i>Legend</i>	<i>Residue combinations</i>
T ₁	Cow-dung + banana tree + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>
T ₂	Cow-dung + water hyacinth + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>
T ₃	Cow-dung + weeds+ <i>Eisenia foetida</i>
T ₄	Cow-dung + kitchen residues + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>
T ₅	Cow-dung + tea green leaf under trough + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>
T ₆	Cow-dung + tea waste + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>
T ₇	Cow-dung + straw + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>

Table 1: Treatment legend and residue combinations of the vermicompost in the seven vermicomposting systems

Construction of the vermicompost station

A commercial large scale vermicompost house/ unit of 5 ft × 20 ft × 20 ft (l×w×h) had already been built in a shaded area of Luskerpore Tea Estate. The vermicomposting trough/ bed 10 ft × 4 ft × 1 ft (l×w×h) was set up at the vermicompost house/unit for culturing the Redworms. The concrete trough/bed had drainage holes (2×2 cm²) to facilitate effective water drainage as vermiwash. The roof of the station was made of zinc sheets with underneath isolation paper to ensure a cool environment with no walls but covered by jute sags to facilitate air flow.

Collection of raw materials

Before the preparation of the culture bed, Redworm (*Eisenia foetida*), cow-dung, banana plant, water hyacinth and straw were collected from local sources. Weeds were collected from tea sections by the hand weeding method and kitchen residues were collected from nearby houses on the tea estate. From the tea factory of the Luskerpore tea estate green leaves under trough and tea waste were collected.

Preparation of the culture bed

At first raw cow-dung was kept for 5-10 days for preconditioning. The first layer of approximately 4 inches of chopped banana plants/ water hyacinth/ weeds/ kitchen residues/ tea green leaf/ tea waste/ straw was kept as bedding materials at the bottom of the bed. The second layer was made of cow-dung, about 4 inches deep. The 3rd layer and the 4th layer were repeated as the same as the 1st and 2nd layers (Figure 1).

Each bed contains 600 kg cow-dung and 400 kg of green vegetation or residues as raw materials as per requirement. In this study, beds of vermicompost were inoculated in 3 phases. About 2-3 kg (2000-3000 in number) Redworm (*Eisenia foetida*) was released on the upper layer of each bed. Water was sprinkled immediately after the release of worms. Beds were kept moist by the sprinkling of water twice a week, depending on the moisture content of the beds. Approximately 60% -70% of the moisture was maintained throughout the experiment. Each bed was turned once every 15 days to maintain aeration and proper decomposition up to the harvest of the vermicompost.

Fig. 1. Setup of culture bed for vermicomposting

Harvesting of vermicompost

Vermicompost was harvested from each bed after the completion of 60 days when raw materials were completely decomposed and it appeared black to dark gray in color as well as granular in physical condition. Seven days prior to harvesting, the watering of the bed was stopped so that the Redworm in the top layer would move down for moisture. The material was collected from the beds in pyramidal heaps for about 24 - 48 hours. The semi-dried vermicompost from the top of the bed was collected and sieved to remove any inert materials. The concentrated vermiculture (Redworms) remained at the bottom where they were counted, weighted, and used again for vermicomposting. When cow-dung was partially decomposed, it was kept over a heap for about two to three days so that redworms could migrate from cow-dung to compost. The sieved vermicompost was dried in the shade area for 12 hours and bagged for weight in kilograms. Vermicompost productivity was calculated in percentage using the formula provided by Ramnarain *et al.* [3].

Redworm harvesting and counting

The Redworm was cultured for 60 days in each bed using different raw materials and cow-dung. The Redworm population was counted in 15 days, 30 days, 45 days and 60 days by manual methods. In the manual harvesting method, Redworm was sorted directly from the compost by hand. This process can be facilitated by taking advantage of the fact that worms avoid light. The material containing worms was dumped in a pile on a flat surface with light for easy sorting. For counting the Redworm population, vermicompost was harvested from the first area of each bed. Then the Redworms were physically separated and counted from the vermicompost. In 60 days during the counting, Redworm was categorized into juvenile, non-clitellate and clitellate with their numbers (Table:02). The total amount of Redworm was weighted after the harvest of vermicompost.

Physical and chemical analysis of vermicompost

The moisture content (%) and dry matter content (%) was determined by using a moisture analyzer (KERN. Model: DBS60-3). According to Yeomans and Bremner [12] the loss on ignition (LOI %) or O.M% and ash content (%) was determined by using Muffle Furnace at 550°C (JISICO. Model: J-FM-28). The pH of vermicompost was determined in compost-water suspension (1:10) using a pH meter according to Jodice *et al.* [13]. Organic carbon content was determined by wet oxidation method [14] while total nitrogen (N) was determined by Micro Kjeldahl steam distillation

method [15]. Total P was determined by the colorimetric method (Blue color method) using a spectrophotometer [16]; total potassium (K), total calcium (Ca), total magnesium (Mg), total zinc (Zn) and total sulfur (S) were determined by the nitric acid - perchloric acid digestion method [15] using the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) (Analytikjena. Model: novAA 400P).

All the data were analyzed statistically by IBM SPSS 20. The data were analyzed using one-way ANOVA and the Analysis of Variance of Simple Classification. Treatments that were significant were analyzed with the Duncan post hoc test at 5% level. The dendrogram grouping for cluster analysis was performed by IBM SPSS.

For economic analysis, the capital cost for building up the vermicompost station (which had been established before) was collected as secondary data. The fixed cost and the variable cost were primary data from the production process. Benefits-cost ratios were calculated for every treatment to find out the most cost-effective quality vermicompost.

Results and Discussion

From tea estate monthly weather data of 2020 the average environmental temperature minimum and maximum as well as humidity data were collected as the secondary data. The collected data was recorded as average environmental temperature was 28°C, where the minimum and maximum temperatures varied from 12°-19°C and 27°-30°C, respectively. The humidity was about 87%, which was in the range of 85%-92% for the rapid growth of Redworm.

Redworm population

The Redworm population was counted by hand sorting method of 1 ft³ area of each bed. During the counting body length and weights of Redworm were measured. The average ranges of length were 2.5 cm to 12 cm and body weight were 0.5 gm to 0.8 gm, respectively. An approximately 900-1200 adult Redworms per kg of vermicompost was estimated. During inoculation of a new bed, about 2 to 3 kg (3000-4000 in number) of Redworm were released and after 60 days about 5.5-8.5 kg (8500-10000 in number) of Redworm were collected, where the average increase rate of Redworm was about 150-175% with conversion rate 1500-1800 worms/2 month. Generally, about 1.0 kg of Redworm needed to convert and consume one kg of waste in a week. Previous research reported that 0.5 kg (1 lb) of Redworm can process about 0.5 kg (1 lb) of organic matter at 75-85% moisture and produce 0.25 kg vermicompost per day (40-50% conversion rate) [17,18].

Legend	Treatments Residue combinations	Redworm categories			Total
		Juvenile	Non-clitellate	Clitellate	
T ₁	Cow-dung + banana tree + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>	395	120	25	540
T ₂	Cow-dung + water hyacinth + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>	425	75	20	520
T ₃	Cow-dung + weeds+ <i>Eisenia foetida</i>	430	40	30	500
T ₄	Cow-dung + kitchen residues + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>	450	70	30	550
T ₅	Cow-dung + tea green leaf under trough + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>	410	75	17	502

T ₆	Cow-dung + tea waste + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>	400	60	38	498
T ₇	Cow-dung + straw + <i>Eisenia foetida</i>	370	80	25	475

Table 2: Redworm categories of the vermicompost in the seven vermicomposting systems

At the end of the 60 days, Redworm were categorized and counted as juvenile, non-clitellate and clitellate by the hand count method as presented in table 2. The total number of red worms per square feet was estimated to be 540, 520, 500, 550, 502, 498 and 475 in T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7, respectively, but the difference between the treatments was statistically insignificant that’s mean there were no relationship among the treatment and the redworm categories.

Productivity

In all treatments, a total of about 1000 kg of raw materials was used (600 kg of cow-dung and 400 kg of green materials or others). The total amount of vermicompost were produced from 630 kg to 718 kg by seven treatments, which productivity percentage was 63.00% to 71.80% (Figure 2). Ramnarain *et al.* [3] reported that the highest productivity of vermicompost was 66.20% produced from grass, followed by rice straw and grass, 52.1% and rice straw, 45.30% respectively; which was due to high fiber content and succulent raw materials. The higher percentage of productivity mainly depends on organic matter content of raw cowdung, redworm amount as well as succulent and fiber content of green materials and organic waste [3]. The highest and lowest amounts of vermicompost were produced in the cases of treatments T4 and T6, respectively. There was no difference on productivity% between T1 and T4, and T3 and T7. However, the productivity among the seven treatments was statistically significant ($F = 45.005, p \leq 0.05$).

Fig. 2. Effects of different treatment on the productivity of vermicompost.

Physical properties

Vermicomposts produced from different materials were nongranular in physical condition, having no odors and colors assorted from dark gray to black, as well as homogenous in nature. Some other properties such as the percentage of moisture, dry matter (%), loss of ignition (%) and ash (%), ranged from 11.16 to 25.41%, 74.59 to 88.84%, 23.39 to 32.82 and 67.18 to 76.61, respectively, which was within the government approve optimum range (Physical condition : Non-Granular, Color: Dark grey to Black, Odor : Absence of foul odour, Moisture% : 10-20%,) (Table 3).LOI=Loss on ignition; Treatment legends are described in Table 1.

Treatment	Physical condition	Odor	Color	Moisture (%)	Dry matter (%)	LOI (%)	Ash (%)
T ₁	Non-Granular	Nil	Dark gray	19.56	80.44	24.60	75.40
T ₂	Non-Granular	Nil	Dark gray	25.41	74.59	32.08	67.92
T ₃	Non-Granular	Nil	Dark gray	19.32	80.68	23.39	76.61
T ₄	Non-Granular	Nil	Dark gray	20.56	79.44	32.03	67.97
T ₅	Non-Granular	Nil	Black	11.16	88.84	23.60	76.40
T ₆	Non-Granular	Nil	Black	20.72	79.28	32.82	67.18
T ₇	Non-Granular	Nil	Dark gray	15.21	84.79	31.30	68.70

**Table 3: Physical properties of the vermicomposts in the seven vermicomposting systems
After 60 days of decomposition**

Chemical properties

From Figure: 03 it has been shown that Chemical properties (A) pH, (B) OC, (C) Total N and (D) C: N ratio of the vermicomposts in the seven systems; and Different small letters indicated significant differences at $p \leq 0.05$. Bars represented standard deviation. The straight line indicated the lowest level of acceptable limit and the dashed line indicated the highest level of acceptable limit of nutrients as recommended by the Government of Bangladesh [19]. Treatment legends are described in Table: 1

Chemical properties such as pH, organic carbon (OC), total nitrogen (N) and Carbon to Nitrogen ratio (C: N) of the produced vermicomposts are presented in Figure 3. The results of the analysis of variance revealed that the effects of raw materials on pH, ($^{ANOVA}F=298.585$, $p \leq 0.05$), OC ($^{ANOVA}F= 1833.592$, $p \leq 0.05$), total N ($^{ANOVA}F= 17.478$, $p \leq 0.05$) and C: N ratio ($^{ANOVA}F= 8.962$, $p \leq 0.05$) in vermicompost was significant at 5% level. The results indicated that vermicompost produced from kitchen residues (T₄) and from tea green leaf under trough (T₅) had the highest (7.92) and lowest (6.15) values of pH, which is slightly alkaline and slightly acidic in nature (Figure 3). [20] Edwards and Bohlen reported that the pH range of vermicompost between 6.0 to 7.0 promotes the availability of plant nutrients like N, P, K. Because of the pH level, vermicompost acts as a buffering agent and increases the cation exchange capacity of the soil. [20] Edwards and Bohlen also stated that, the increased pH level of vermicompost can be due to the increased content of mineral N in the primary substrate. On the other hand, the result shows that there were no differences observed in pH values among treatments T₂, T₄ and T₇.

Vermicompost produced from tea waste (T₆) and weed (T₃) had the highest (19.08%) and lowest (13.60%) values of OC (Figure 3); where there was no differences on OC value between Water hyacinth (T₂) and kitchen wastes (T₄) 18.65% and 18.62% respectively. Vermicompost produced from the tea waste (T₆) and tea green leaf under trough (T₅) had the highest (1.96%) and lowest (1.32%) values of total N, where there was no differences between kitchen waste (T₄) and straw (T₇) as well as weeds (T₃) and Banana tree (T₁) 1.90% to 1.89% and 1.39% to 1.35% respectively. The organic carbon and total N content of the produced vermicompost were within the range of government's recommended permissible limit i.e. about 10 - 25% for OC and 0.5 - 4.0% for total N. During the process of vermicomposting, the earthworms feed on the organic matter and microbial degradation takes place. The percentage of OC was reduced after vermicomposting, indicating that the earthworms accelerated the decomposition of the organic matter. Carbon is a

major component of organic molecules, which are the building blocks of all organisms and, thus, are needed as a source of energy for the composting process [9, 21, 22].

In terms of C: N (Figure 3), though the highest value of 10.60 was found for T1 and the lowest value of 9.60 for T7, the result also showed that (T2= 10.30 and T5= 10.44) as well as (T3= 9.78, T4= 9.80 and T6= 9.74) had no differences among them. Research by [23] Senesi states that a decline of C: N to less than 20 indicates an advanced degree of maturity in organic waste. [24] Ludibeth *et al.* also reported that microbial respiration and nitrogenous excretion reduce the C: N of the substrate because the source of carbon in dried plant material and cow dung provides N input during the decomposition process.

Fig. 3: Effect of different Treatment on Chemical Properties of Vermicompost. [OC (organic carbon), N (nitrogen)]

Nutrient properties of produced vermicompost

From figure: 4 it had been shown that, Nutrient properties (A) Total P ($ANOVA F= 88.000, p\leq 0.05$), (B) Total K ($ANOVA F= 255.187, p\leq 0.05$), (C) Total Ca ($ANOVA F= 56.597, p\leq 0.05$), (D) Total Mg ($ANOVA F= 131.624, p\leq 0.05$), (E) Total S ($ANOVA F= 22.032, p\leq 0.05$) and (F) Total Zn ($ANOVA F= 6.109, p\leq 0.05$) of the vermicomposts in the seven systems as well as Different small letters indicated significant differences at $p\leq 0.05$. Bars represented standard deviation. The straight line indicated the

lowest level of acceptable limit and the dashed line indicated the highest level of the acceptable limit of nutrients as recommended by the Government of Bangladesh [19]. Treatment legends are described in Table 1.

The results of the analysis of variance showed that the effects of raw materials on total P in vermicomposting were highly significant at the 5% level. Figure 4 depicts the total P values, with kitchen residues (T4) made vermicompost having the highest value and water hyacinth (T2) made vermicompost having the lowest value of 1.60% and 1.12%, respectively. The result also shows that there was a significant difference in the P content among the treatments T1, T2, T5, T6 and T7, whereas there was no difference on their value range between T3 and T4.

During the vermicomposting process, earthworms change the insoluble P to the soluble form via the phosphatase enzyme present in their gut, which can make P more available to the plants. Ghosh *et al.* [25] reported that the main reason for the increased P during the vermicomposting process is the presence of alkaline phosphatase enzymes in the cast of earthworms. The difference in the P concentration among the treatments might be due to the quality of the raw materials used for produce vermicompost as large amount of phosphorus available in worm faces [25, 27].

The results of statistical analysis (Figure 4) showed that the effects of raw materials on total K were highly significant at a probability of less than 0.05, where vermicompost from kitchen residues (T4) had the highest value of 1.32% and the lowest value of 0.62% for weeds (T3). There was a significant difference between the treatments of the beds.

Vermicompost is rich in plant nutrients, provides all essential nutrient elements and releases exchangeable and available forms of plant nutrients such as phosphates, exchangeable Ca and soluble K. Suther [26] stated that vermicompost contains a high concentration of exchangeable K due to enhanced microbial activity during the vermicomposting process, which enhances the mineralization rate.

The content of total Ca and total Mg in vermicompost is indicative of its nutrient value. T4 had a total Ca of 0.90%, T5 and T6 had a total Ca of 0.50%, T3 had a total Ca of 0.09%, and T2 had a total Ca of 0.04%. There were significant differences among the treatments for both Ca and Mg. The values are presented in Figure 4, where kitchen residues (T4) made into vermicompost had the highest values in all cases of indicated properties.

The concentration of both macro and micronutrients such as S and Zn in vermicompost showed that the effects of treatments on the nutrient properties were highly significant at a 5% level. The values are presented in Figure 4, where for S concentration kitchen residues (T4) made vermicompost had the highest value (0.10%) and T2 had the lowest value (0.02%), as well as for Zn concentration T4, had the highest value (0.05%) with (0.01%) as the lowest value for T5 in all cases of indicated properties. From Figure 4, it was also revealed that there were no differences on their value range among all treatments except T2 and T4 for total S whereas there were no differences on their value range among all treatments except T4 and T5 for total Zn content.

The findings of the present study indicated that the content of all the macro and micro elements as well as the physical properties of the produced vermicompost were within the government-approved permissible range (Phosphorous (P) = 0.5-3.0%, Potassium (K) = 0.5-3.0% and Zn = 0.1% (max)).

Fig. 4. Effect of different Treatment on Nutrient Properties of Vermicompost. [P (Phosphorus), K (Potassium), Ca (Calcium), Mg (Magnesium), S (Sulphur), Zn (Zinc)]

Benefit-cost analysis

The benefit-cost analysis of vermicomposting is presented in Table 4. The total capital expenditure was about USD 2448.27 was collected as secondary data from the garden. All other expenditure was primary data generated during the experiment. This analysis shows that T4 (kitchen residues) produced the highest amount (2154 kg) of vermicompost with a production cost per kg USD 0.10 (lowest), where T6 (tea waste) produced the lowest (1890 kg) of vermicompost

with a production cost per kg USD 0.12, but with the same cost of production per kg T3 (weeds) produced (2040 kg) of vermicompost. On the other hand, though T5 (tea green leaf under the trough) produced 1950 kg of vermicompost, its production cost per kg was lower than T3 (weeds) and T6 (tea waste), which was USD 0.11. The percentage of benefit-cost ratio was estimated at 49.15% (highest) for T4 and 2.98% (lowest) for T7.

Variables	Treatments						
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₆	T ₇
Fixed cost (USD)	44.64	44.64	44.64	38.88	38.88	38.88	44.64
Variable cost (USD)	35.04	37.44	30.24	30.24	30.24	30.24	35.04
Production cost (USD)	79.68	82.08	74.88	69.12	69.12	69.12	79.68
Total production cost for 3 beds (USD)	239.04	246.24	224.64	207.36	207.36	207.36	239.04
Depreciation cost (USD)				10.50			
Actual expenditure (USD)	249.54	256.74	235.14	217.86	217.86	217.86	249.54
Average production kg/bed	690	700	680	718	650	630	670
Total production form 3 bed kg	2070	2100	2040	2154	1950	1890	2010
Market price of vermicompost per kg (USD)				0.25			
Total value of produced vermicompost (USD)	521.64	529.20	514.08	542.81	491.40	476.28	506.52
Benefit (USD)	272.10	272.46	278.94	324.95	273.54	258.42	256.98
Cost per kg (USD)	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.10	0.11	0.12	0.12
Benefit per kg (USD)	0.13	0.13	0.14	0.15	0.14	0.14	0.13
Benefit-cost Ratio (%)	9.04	6.12	18.63	49.15	25.56	18.62	2.98

Table 4: Benefit-cost analysis for the vermicomposts in the seven vermicomposting systems

Treatment legends are described in (Table 1) 1 USD (US Dollar) = 85.80 BDT (Bangladesh Taka)

Total capital expenditure for the establishment of the vermicompost station = USD 2520 (secondary data)

Let the establishment be usable for 20 years.

Depreciation cost of total capital expenditure per month = (2520 ÷ 240) (20*12 months)
= USD 10.50

Production cost = Fixed cost + Variable cost

Actual expenditure = Total production cost + Depreciation cost of total capital expenditure per month

Benefit = Total value of produced vermicompost (USD) - Actual expenditure (USD)

Cost per Kg (USD) = Actual expenditure (USD) ÷ Total production of vermicompost

Benefit per kg (USD) = Total production from 3 beds ÷ Benefit

Benefit-cost ratio (%) =
$$\frac{(\text{Benefit per kg} - \text{Cost per Kg}) \times 100}{\text{Cost per Kg}}$$

In this study, the hierarchical analysis showed that T4 is a separated cluster from the other treatments when all the parameters were considered together. Therefore, treatment T4 could be adopted for the vermicomposting for the tea industry in Bangladesh soils as it manifested to be a cost-effective and energy-efficient treatment.

Fig. 5. Dendrogram showing similarities of vermicompost properties after vermicomposting in the seven systems. Treatment legends are described in Table 1.

Conclusion

The nutritive value of vermicompost mostly depends on the types, nature and purity of raw materials used in vermicomposting, as well as the amount of Redworm used per bed and proper maintenance methods. The mixture of different raw materials with the activity of *Eisenia foetida* including their growth, multiplication, reproduction, nutrition and finally leads to the production of quality vermicompost by low cost or cost-effective methods. It was dark gray to black in color and was homogenous in nature. From the nutritional point of view, the vermicompost had an adequate amount of essential macro and micro nutrients like N, P, K, Ca, Mg, Zn, S, as well as pH, OC, etc. The low production cost (cost per kg) and high benefit (benefit per kg) with a positive benefit-cost ratio of produced vermicompost by the experiment indicate the achievement of getting a sustainable nutrient-rich organic fertilizer that can be recommended for the tea industry of Bangladesh. Therefore, vermicompost produced by treatment T4 (Cowdung + Kitchen Residues + *Eisenia foetida*) could be adopted for the vermicomposting for the tea industry in Bangladesh being manifested to be a cost-effective and energy-efficient treatment. This may have a considerable effect on the vegetative growth and yield of both young tea and mature tea, as well as on soil properties which will be done by future research.

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